

Some Zinc (II) Complexes with Substituted Pyridines

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Ethanollic solutions of zinc salts, ZnX_2 , where X is chloride, bromide and thiocyanate were reacted with several substituted pyridines (L) viz., 3-chloro, 3-bromo, 3-ethyl, 4-ethyl and 4-cyano-pyridines and a number of complexes having the general formula ZnL_2X_2 were isolated. They were characterised on the basis of their analyses, conductance and infrared spectral data.

MANY zinc complexes have been reported^{1,2} earlier using substituted pyridines as ligands. Allan *et al*³ have reported a number of zinc complexes with mono and disubstituted pyridines. In this communication we report a number of zinc(II) complexes having the general formula ZnL_2X_2 , where L is 3-chloro, 3-bromo, 3-ethyl, 4-ethyl and 4-cyano pyridines and X is chloride, bromide or thiocyanate.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Ethanollic solutions of zinc salts were reacted separately with different substituted pyridines in 1:2 ratio and on shaking white crystalline compounds separated out. These compounds were suction filtered, washed with alcohol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal, halogen or thiocyanate and nitrogen by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a double beam Unicam SP-200 spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical, melting point and conductance data are given in Table 1; Infrared spectra data are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present communication have a general composition on ZnL_2X_2 and are presumably tetrahedral. All the compounds are white crystalline solids, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are non-electrolytes, Λ_M being of the order of 8-15 mhos (Table 1). Infrared spectra show that most of the absorption bands due to free ligands are modified in the respective complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. The $Zn(4-CNpy)_2Cl_2$ complex was reported⁵ earlier but detailed investigations were lacking. The ligand 4-cyano pyridine can be bonded to the metal either through the pyridine nitrogen or through the nitrile nitrogen. The preparation and infra-red examination of 2-, 3-, and 4-cyano pyridine complexes of Cu(I), Ag(I) and Au(I) have earlier been reported⁶. It was concluded that in 3- and 4-cyano pyridine complexes, the metals were bound to the pyridine nitrogen and in 2-cyano pyridine complex the bonding was through the nitrile nitrogen. In the present case, had the bonding taken place through the nitrile nitrogen then the band at 1546 cm^{-1} in the free ligand attributable to $\nu(C-C)+\nu(C-N)$ should have shifted to a lower frequency. This is not observed in the 4-cyanopyridine complexes reported now (Table 2) and on the other hand, there

TABLE I. ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF ZINC(II) COMPLEXES WITH SUBSTITUTED PYRIDINES

Compound	M.P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos)	% Zinc		% Halogen or thiocyanate		% Nitrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
$ZnCl_2(4\text{-et.py})_2$	94	14.8	18.47	18.31	19.54	19.89	7.46	7.98
$ZnBr_2(4\text{-et.py})_2$	100	11.3	14.86	14.87	35.96	36.34	5.88	6.37
$Zn(NCS)_2(4\text{-et.py})_2$	145	12.1	16.44	16.52	28.77	29.32	13.75	14.14
$ZnCl_2(3\text{-et.py})_2$	107	12.4	18.01	18.31	19.54	19.89	7.38	7.98
$ZnBr_2(3\text{-et.py})_2$	120	10.4	14.74	14.87	36.52	36.34	5.92	6.37
$Zn(NCS)_2(3\text{-et.py})_2$	124	11.6	16.40	16.52	28.97	29.32	13.68	14.14
$ZnCl_2(3\text{-br.py})_2$	145	9.4	14.33	14.45	15.55	15.70	5.82	6.19
$ZnBr_2(3\text{-br.py})_2$	158	8.1	11.84	12.09	29.01	29.54	4.55	5.18
$Zn(NCS)_2(3\text{-br.py})_2$	151	7.8	12.94	13.14	23.25	23.33	10.85	11.27
$ZnCl_2(3\text{-cl.py})_2$	125	11.1	18.69	18.84	19.38	19.54	7.16	7.71
$ZnBr_2(3\text{-cl.py})_2$	134	9.6	14.26	14.45	35.17	35.34	5.76	6.19
$ZnCl_2(4\text{-cN.py})_2$	213	12.1	18.66	19.04	20.06	20.67	15.65	16.31
$ZnBr_2(4\text{-cN.py})_2$	228	10.1	14.89	15.09	36.47	36.89	12.28	12.93

is a slight shift to a higher frequency. So the bonding has presumably taken place through pyridine nitrogen but not through nitrile nitrogen which is in conformity with the earlier observations⁶.

TABLE 2. INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (ν IN cm^{-1})

Compounds	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ + $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{R})$ + $\beta(\text{C}-\text{H})$
	4-cyanopyridine	1546 w	1594 s
$\text{ZnCl}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1550 s	1600 vs	1208 vs
$\text{ZnBr}_2(4\text{-CN.py})_2$	1555 s	1618 vs	1220 vs
		$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$
$\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2(3\text{-et.py})_2$		810 vs	2065 vs
$\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2(4\text{-et.py})_2$		825 vs	2060 vs
$\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2(3\text{-br.py})_2$		800 vs	2040 vs

w—weak; s—sharp; vs—very sharp.

The absorption bands attributable to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in case of thiocyanato complexes are recorded in Table 2. Livingstone⁷ pointed out that the thiocyanate ion generally co-ordinates to class 'a' metals through nitrogen and to class 'b' metals through sulphur. Criteria for establishing the mode of bonding in thiocyanato complexes have been worked out based on the frequency ranges found for the three vibrational modes of thiocyanate ion i.e., $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ ⁸, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ ^{9,10,11} and the degenerate bonding mode $\delta(\text{NCS})$ ^{11,12,13}. The C-S stretching frequency has often been considered diagnostic of the metal ligand bond since $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ is at $690\text{--}720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-SCN and at $780\text{--}860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-NCS complexes. The C-N stretch of a thiocyanate complex increases in the order $\text{CNS}^- < \text{M}-\text{NCS} < \text{M}-\text{SCN} < \text{M}-\text{SCN}-\text{M}$. In the case of complexes reported in the present

investigation, the $\delta(\text{NCS})$ could not be recorded as it was beyond the range of the instrument used. But $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ are near about 2100 and 800 cm^{-1} respectively (Table 2) indicative of N-bonded terminal thiocyanate groups. This is in conformity with the recent work^{14,15} on thiocyanate complexes. Hence all the complexes reported in the present investigation are four co-ordinated, presumably having a tetrahedral configuration.

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